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Editor : Kolla Sri Krishnarao

E-mail : parisodhanatelugu@gmail.com

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అందె వెంకటరాజం

“భోగసాగమున దేలి,
భూవలమయు బట్టి యేలి
నరక్తము ద్రాగి తూలి
నర్తించు సంపన్నుడు
కలవారికి చదువు పదవి
కలవారికె ఓటు సీటు
కలవారికె సుఖములన్ని
కలవారికె బతుకు సుమ్మీ”

అని ఘాటుగా ప్రశ్నిస్తూ కులమతాల మధ్య హెచ్చుతగ్గులను ఈసడించిన కవి అందె వెంకటరాజం. అష్టావధాని, కవి శిరోమణిగా ప్రసిద్ధిగాంచిన అందె వెంకటరాజం 1933 సంవత్సరం అక్టోబర్ 14 కరీంనగర్ జిల్లా కోరుట్ల గ్రామంలో లింబయ్య, భూదేవి పుణ్యదంపతులకు జన్మించారు. వీరి విద్యాభ్యాసమంతా స్వగ్రామంలోనే సాగింది. కాకతీయ విశ్వవిద్యాలయంలో ఎం.ఎ తెలుగు, వానమామలై పరదాచార్యుల వారి కృతులు - అనుశీలనము అనే సిద్ధాంత గ్రంథాన్ని సమర్పించి డాక్టరేట్ పొందారు.

విద్యార్థి దశలోనే గ్రాంథిక భాషలో అనేక కవితలు, పాటలు రాశారు. పద్య ప్రక్రియ అందెవారిని ఆకట్టుకుంది. పద్య ప్రక్రియలోనే రచనలు కొనసాగించారు. అవధాన ప్రక్రియలో ప్రవేశించి 88 పైగా అష్టావధానాలను పూర్తి చేశారు. వీరు వచన కవిత మినహా మిగతా సాహితీ ప్రక్రియలన్నింటిలో రచనలు చేశారు. వీరి రచనలలో భారతరాణి, నవోదయము, మణి మంజూష, భువన విజయము, మానసవీణ, ఈశ్వర వతకము, మాధవవర్య, సాహితీజీవన తరంగాలు, అవధాన పద్య మంజరి, అర్ధరాత్రి సుప్రభాతం, పసివాని మూడోపెళ్ళి, మైసమ్మ భయం, అంగడి వింతలు, విచిత్రమైన భక్తురాలు, అవధాన పద్య మంజరి, కళా తపస్విని, భజన గీతాలు, శ్రీ గోవిందగిరి తత్య గీతమాల, నింబగిరి నరసింహ, విచిత్ర గాథలు, స్వర్ణ భారతము మొదలగునవి వీరి ప్రసిద్ధ రచనలు.

వీరి విశిష్ట సాహిత్య సేవలకు గాను అవధాన యువకేసరి, అవధాన చతురానన, కవి శిరోమణి మొదలగు గౌరవ బిరుదలు, సత్కారాలు పొందారు. కోరుట్ల డిగ్రీ కళాశాలలో తెలుగు ఉపన్యాసకులుగా పదవీ బాధ్యతలు నిర్వర్తించి పదవీ విరమణ చేశారు. వీరు విశ్రాంత జీవితంలో కూడా అవిశ్రాంతంగా తెలుగు సాహిత్యానికి విశేష సేవలు చేస్తూ 2006వ సంవత్సరం సెప్టెంబర్ 11న పరమపదించారు.

- సంపాదకవర్గం

Contents (విషయ సూచిక)

1. చారిత్రక అడుగులు ముంగారు మొలకలు	- బల్లా గురురాధాదేవి	6
2. తెలంగాణ కుల అస్థిత్వ నవలలు - సామాజిక దృక్పథం	- భీమరాం దిలీప్ చంద్ర	10
3. జాషువా సాహిత్యం - భారత దార్శనికత	- డా॥ కొల్లేటి రవిబాబు	16
4. కర్పూర వసంత రాయలు - సిసారె సాహితీ వైభవం	- కొయ్యా శ్రీనివాసులు	21
5. తెలంగాణ సాయుధ పోరాటకవిత్వం: 'జాతీయత' (1946-1951)	- డా॥ చంద్రయ్య ఎస్	27
6. మువ్వ శ్రీనివాసరావు సమాంతర ఛాయలు - ప్రపంచీకరణ	- గంట అశోక్	35
7. దళిత పద్య సాహిత్యం - సామాజికాంశాల విశ్లేషణ	- డా॥ సిద్ధార్థ మద్దిరాల	39
8. బౌద్ధమతంలో సరస్వతీ ఆరాధనా శిల్పలక్షణములు	- శ్రీవైష్ణవ వేణుగోపాల్	44
9. సిరా కవిత్వం - ప్రపంచీకరణ	- దత్తి రామారావు	49
10. మల్లిపురం జగదీశ్ కథలు - పాత్ర చిత్రణ	- డా॥ పాలగడ్డ మైనావతి	52
11. ఆధునిక వచన కవిత్వంలో జోగిని	- పేరం అమ్మతరావు	56
12. Learning Management System in Higher Education : Opportunities and Challenges	- Mr. Akhilesh Kumar	60
13. Role of Women Journalists in Promoting Social Issues for the Development of Society	- Devender Bhardwaj	72
14. An Emergence of Restructuring Teaching-Learning of English Speaking Skillsof Odia Medium Secondary School Students : An Instrumental Case Study	-Dr. Pratap Kumar Dash & - Dr. Anup Kumar Kujur	78
15. Attitude of Scheduled Tribe Students towards Studies having Differential Levels of Home Environment	- Santosh Subba, - Dr. Vimal Kishor & - Dr. TJMS Raju	91
16. Traditional Village Administration of the Aimol Tribe of Manipur	- Leivon Chungsanglien	101
17. Indian Women Writers : Struggle and Emergence	- Md Shamim Ashraf & - Dr. Samir Khan	108
18. Trajectory of Muslim Political Representation in India : Responsiveness of Political Parties in Telangana	- Mohammad Rizwan Rasheed	112

Attitude of Scheduled Tribe Students towards Studies having Differential Levels of Home Environment

- *Santosh Subba*

Research Scholar, Department of Education, School of Professional Studies, Sikkim University (A Central University), 6th Mile, Samdur, PO Tadong, Gangtok, Sikkim.

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Associate Professor, Department of Education, School of Education, Central University of Jharkhand, Cheri-Manatu, Kanke, Ranchi.

Dr. TJMS Raju

Associate Professor, Department of Education, School of Professional Studies, Sikkim University (A Central University), 6th Mile, Samdur, PO Tadong, Gangtok, Sikkim.

Abstract :

The main objective of the present research was to study the attitude of scheduled tribe secondary school students towards studies having differential levels of home environment. The sample comprised of 400 scheduled tribe secondary school students out of which 200 male and 200 were female students. For the present study the Attitude towards Studies Scale developed and standardized by the investigator and Home Environment Scale constructed and standardized by A. Akhtar and S.B. Saxena was used to meet the objectives. To test the hypotheses one way ANOVA i.e. analysis of variance followed by 't' test has been used. The results revealed that male, female and total scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of attitude towards studies differ significantly with respect to their mean scores on home environment.

Introduction :

India is a pluralist country, with rich diversity, reflected in the multitude of cultures, religions, languages and racial stocks. The Indian population includes different castes, communities and social groups. India, with a population 1.21 billion (2011 census) has the single larg-

est tribal population in the world, constituting 8.6% of the total population of the country. The most tribal populous states are Mizoram (94.75 per cent), Lakshadweep (93.15 per cent), Nagaland (87.70 per cent), and Meghalaya (85.53 per cent). However, the states of Madhya Pradesh, Orissa, Bihar, Maharashtra, Gujarat, Rajasthan, Andhra Pradesh, Sikkim and West Bengal also have much tribal population all over India. Scheduled Tribe of India have struggled hard for their survival and development since the pre independence period. The Scheduled Tribes had suffered physical isolation, remote from civilization, and have therefore maintained the cultural uniqueness. Consequently, this group of people lag far behind others in terms of social and economic development. The Constitution of India had rightly recognized this group of people as weaker sections of society, based on their socio-economic backwardness and the age-old social discrimination and physical isolation that they had been subjected to. Sikkim is such a state where the tribal population is very high and life is comparatively very hard here due to its geographic and other climatic conditions. Out of the total population of 610,577 (according to 2011 cen-

sus) in Sikkim the tribal population happens to be 33.8% (Tribal Profile at a Glance, 2013, p.5.). Currently, the tribal group of this region lags behind not only the general awareness about education but also on the issues like low literacy and indulge in anti-social activities (like drug abuse). Pimpley (1980) has revealed in his study that scheduled tribe students are mostly backward because of many factors like parent's illiteracy, financial crisis and most importantly they usually indulge themselves in performing domestic duties. The overall development of the state Sikkim depends upon the education of the people of Sikkim and for which the role of the parents is quite crucial. The parents are expected to encourage the youths especially the secondary school going students those are expected to play a very decisive role in nation building process. The proper conducive environment affects a number of psycho-social constructs e.g. educational aspirations, adjustment, achievement motivation and attitude towards studies etc. The present study highlighted the status of attitude of scheduled tribe students towards studies having differential levels of home environment.

Objectives of the study :

The present study has been conducted keeping in mind the following objectives like:

1. To compare the attitude of male scheduled tribe secondary school students towards studies having differential levels of home environment.
2. To compare the attitude of female scheduled tribe secondary school students towards studies having differential levels of home environment.

3. To compare the attitude of scheduled tribe secondary school students towards studies having differential levels of home environment.

Hypotheses of the study :

The hypotheses formulated and tested in the present study were as follows :

1. Male scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment differ significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies.
2. Femalescheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment differ significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies.
3. Scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment differ significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies.

Research Method :

In the present study, descriptive survey method was used.

Statistical techniques used :

In order to test the hypotheses of the present study, the investigator used one way ANOVA i.e. analysis of variance followed by 't' test.

Sample :

In the present study the sample of 400 (200 male and 200 female) scheduled tribe secondary school students were selected by employing stratified random sampling from four districts of Sikkim state. These students were selected from twenty schools of four districts.

Tools used :

In the present study Attitude towards Studies Scale developed and standardized by the investigator was used. The tool was scored in a 5 point continuum having the options *Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree*. The scale contained 24 negative items and 21 positive items. All positive items were scored according to the following sequence: 5 (Strongly Agree), 4 (Agree), 3 (Undecided) 2 (Disagree) and 1 (Strongly Disagree) and vice versa scoring for negative items.

For ascertaining the level of home environment of the scheduled tribe secondary students the investigator used the Home Environment Scale constructed and standardized by S.B. Saxena.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data :

- A. Study of Significance of Difference among the Mean Scores on Attitude towards Studies of Male Scheduled Tribe Secondary School Students having High, Average and Low Levels of Home Environment

The present study aimed to find out whether the male scheduled tribe secondary school stu-

dents having high, average and low levels of home environment differs on their mean scores on attitude towards studies or not. The data were obtained from scheduled tribe secondary school students to find out the difference in the mean scores on attitude towards studies of scheduled tribe secondary school students having differential levels of home environment. Further, the investigator categorized the male scheduled tribe secondary school students into three categories on the basis of their levels of home environment scores.

As such, the male students scoring 149 or above, in between 111-148 and 110 or below than it were considered as the students having high, average and low levels of home environment respectively. In order to find out the differences in mean scores on attitude towards studies of the male scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment, their respective scores on attitude towards studies were taken into consideration and the significance of difference among the mean values of these three levels of scores have been calculated by means of adopting one way analysis of variance or f-test. The results obtained subsequently have been presented in table-1.

Table - 1

F-value for Male Scheduled Tribe Secondary School Students having High, Average and Low Levels of Home Environment in respect of the Variable of Attitude towards Studies

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square (Variance)	F-ratio
Between groups	4294.62	2	2147.31	5.45**
Within groups	77974.59	197	393.81	
Total	82269.20	199		

The above table-1 shows that the sum of squares between groups and within groups have been found to be 4294.62 and 77974.59 respectively and mean squares between groups and within groups have been found to be 2147.31 and 393.81 respectively. The f-value has been found to be 5.45 being significant at 0.01 level of significance.

It indicates that there is significant difference in the mean scores on attitude towards studies of the male scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment. Hence, the hypothesis that “Male scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment differ significantly

with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies” is accepted.

An analysis of the table-1 reveals that the male scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment differ significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies. But it is not clear that which of the two groups differs. Therefore, it is necessary to calculate the significance of mean difference of the different groups such as high vs. average, high vs. low and average vs. low. The data pertaining to the significant of mean difference between the mean scores of the respective groups have been presented in the table-2.

Table-2

t-value for male scheduled tribe secondary school students having different levels of home environment in respect of the Variable of Attitude towards Studies

Category	N	M	SD	SE _M	df	t	Remarks
High vs. Average	33	163.32	19.70	3.94	167	1.63	Not Significant
	136	156.36	19.76	1.65			
High vs. Low	33	163.32	19.70	3.94	62	3.05	Sig. at 0.01
	31	146.90	20.33	3.65			
Average vs. Low	136	156.36	19.76	1.65	165	2.41	Sig. at 0.05
	31	146.90	20.33	3.65			

From the analysis of table-2 it is concluded that the two groups namely high vs. low and average vs. low differs significantly on their attitude towards studies as the obtained ‘t’ ratio of the respective groups are found to be significant at 0.01 and 0.05 level with df value 62 and 165 respectively. Therefore, we can infer that the home environment of male scheduled tribe secondary school students is having some bearing on the attitude towards studies.

B. Study of Significance of Difference among the Mean Scores on Attitude towards Studies of Female Scheduled Tribe Secondary School Students having High, Average and Low Levels of Home Environment

The present study aimed to find out whether the female scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment differs on their mean scores

on attitude towards studies or not. The data were obtained from scheduled tribe secondary school students to find out the difference in the mean scores on attitude towards studies of scheduled tribe secondary school students having differential levels of home environment. Further, the investigator categorized the female scheduled tribe secondary school students into three categories on the basis of their levels of home environment scores.

As such, the female students scoring 148 or above, in between 117-147 and 116 or below than it were considered as the students having

high, average and low levels of home environment respectively. In order to find out the differences in mean scores on attitude towards studies of the female scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment, their respective scores on attitude towards studies were taken into consideration and the significance of difference among the mean values of these three levels of scores have been calculated by means of adopting one way analysis of variance or f-test. The results obtained subsequently have been presented in table-3.

Table -3

F-value for Female Scheduled Tribe Secondary School Students having High, Average and Low Levels of Home Environment in respect of the Variable of Attitude towards Studies

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square (Variance)	F-ratio
Between groups	4950.32	2	2475.16	6.14**
Within groups	79453.18	197	403.32	
Total	84403.50	199		

The above table-3 shows that the sum of squares between groups and within groups have been found to be 4950.32 and 79453.18 respectively and mean squares between groups and within groups have been found to be 2475.16 and 403.32 respectively. The f-value has been found to be 6.14 being significant at 0.01 level of significance.

It indicates that there is significant difference in the mean scores on attitude towards studies of the female scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment. Hence, the hypothesis that

“Female scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment differ significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies” is accepted.

An analysis of the table-3 reveals that the female scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment differ significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies. But it is not clear that which of the two groups differs. Therefore, it is necessary to cal-

culate the significance of mean difference of the different groups such as high vs. average, high vs. low and average vs. low. The data pertain-

ing to the significant of mean difference between the mean scores of the respective groups have been presented in the table-4.

Table - 4
t-value for female scheduled tribe secondary school students having different levels of home environment in respect of the Variable of Attitude towards Studies

Category	N	M	SD	SE _M	df	t	Remarks
High vs. Average	35	166.80	17.21	2.91	164	2.96	Sig. at 0.01
	131	155.64	20.43	1.79			
High vs. Low	35	166.80	17.21	2.91	67	3.45	Sig. at 0.01
	34	150.68	21.40	3.67			
Average vs. Low	131	155.64	20.43	1.79	163	1.25	Not Significant
	34	150.68	21.40	3.67			

From the analysis of table-4 it is concluded that the two groups namely high vs. average and high vs. low differs significantly on their attitude towards studies as the obtained 't' ratio of the respective groups are found to be significant at 0.01 level with df value 164 and 67 respectively. Therefore, we can infer that the home environment of female scheduled tribe secondary school students is having some bearing on the attitude towards studies.

C. Study of Significance of Difference among the Mean Scores on Attitude towards Studies of Scheduled Tribe Secondary School Students having High, Average and Low Levels of Home Environment

The present study aimed to find out whether the scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment differs on their mean scores on attitude towards studies or not. The data were obtained from scheduled tribe secondary school students to find out the difference in the mean

scores on attitude towards studies of scheduled tribe secondary school students having differential levels of home environment. Further, the investigator categorized the scheduled tribe secondary school students into three categories on the basis of their levels of home environment scores.

As such, students scoring 150 or above, in between 113-149 and 112 or below than it were considered as the students having high, average and low levels of home environment respectively. In order to find out the differences in mean scores on attitude towards studies of the scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment, their respective scores on attitude towards studies were taken into consideration and the significance of difference among the mean values of these three levels of scores have been calculated by means of adopting one way analysis of variance or f-test. The results obtained subsequently have been presented in table-5.

Table -5
F-value for Scheduled Tribe Secondary School Students having High, Average and Low Levels of Home Environment in respect of the Variable of Attitude towards Studies

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square (Variance)	F-ratio
Between groups	7584.47	2	3792.23	9.51**
Within groups	158392.01	397	398.97	
Total	165976.48	399		

The above table-5 shows that the sum of squares between groups and within groups have been found to be 7584.47 and 158392.01 respectively and mean squares between groups and within groups have been found to be 3792.23 and 398.97 respectively. The f-value has been found to be 9.51 being significant at 0.01 level of significance.

It indicates that there is significant difference in the mean scores on attitude towards studies of the scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment. Hence, the hypothesis that “Scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home

environment differ significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies” is accepted.

An analysis of the table-5 reveals that the scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment differ significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies. But it is not clear that which of the two groups differs. Therefore, it is necessary to calculate the significance of mean difference of the different groups such as high vs. average, high vs. low and average vs. low. The data pertaining to the significant of mean difference between the mean scores of the respective groups have been presented in the table-6.

Table-6
t-value for scheduled tribe secondary school students having different levels of home environment in respect of the Variable of Attitude towards Studies

Category	N	M	SD	SE _M	df	t	Remarks
High vs. Average	52	166.25	18.67	2.59	341	3.53	Sig. at 0.01
	291	155.72	20.03	1.17			
High vs. Low	52	166.25	18.67	2.59	107	4.30	Sig. at 0.01
	57	149.90	20.83	2.76			
Average vs. Low	291	155.72	20.03	1.17	346	1.98	Sig. at 0.05
	57	149.90	20.83	2.76			

From the analysis of table-6 it is concluded that the three groups namely high vs. average, high vs. low and average vs. low differs significantly on their attitude towards studies as the obtained 't' ratio of the respective groups are found to be significant at 0.01 and 0.05 level with df value 341, 107 and 346 respectively. Therefore, we can infer that the home environment of scheduled tribe secondary school students is having some bearing on the attitude towards studies.

Findings of the Study :

After careful analysis of the obtained data and interpretation of the result with regard to the objectives and hypotheses of the study, the investigator reached at the following findings:

1. Male scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment differ significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies.
2. Two groups of male scheduled tribe secondary school students namely high vs. low and average vs. low differs significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies.
3. One group of male scheduled tribe secondary school students namely high vs. average do not differs significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies.
4. Female scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment differ significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies.
5. Two groups of female scheduled tribe

secondary school students namely high vs. average and high vs. low differs significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies.

6. One group of female scheduled tribe secondary school students namely average vs. low do not differs significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies.
7. Scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment differ significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies.
8. Three groups of scheduled tribe secondary school students high vs. average, high vs. low and average vs. low differs significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies.

Conclusion :

We can conclude by saying that home environment plays a very vital role in enhancing the attitude of students towards studies. Above stated findings of the study reveals that the scheduled tribe secondary school students having high, average and low levels of home environment differ significantly with respect to their mean scores on attitude towards studies. Therefore, we can say home environment is related to the attitude towards studies of the scheduled tribe students and in order to enhance their attitude the parents should pay attention towards exploring new methods to increase it. The parents and teachers should provide conducive and free environment to the students in order to develop positive attitude towards studies.

Teachers should provide tests to measure the different scholastic and co-scholastic abilities of the students. Proper guidance to the students

should be provided. Parent teacher meetings should be conducted timely to assist the students in their studies.

References :

1. Abu-Hilal, Maher M., Abdelfattah, Faisal, Abduljabbar, Adel, Marsh, Herbert W. (2013). Attitudes toward School, Homework, Subject Matter Value, Self-Concept and Positive Affect: A Structural Equation Model". Retrieved from http://www.iea.nl/sites/default/files/irc/IRC-2013_Abu-Hilal_etal.pdf dated 20-04-17
2. Gautam, Rajni (1990). A study of creativity values, educational achievement and attitude towards education among Scheduled Castes and other castes students. In *Fifth Survey of Research in Education (1972-1978)*. New Delhi, National Council of Educational Research & Training (NCERT). 2000, p. 1639
3. Mary-Anne Holfve-Sabel (2007). A comparison of student attitudes towards school, teachers and peers in Swedish comprehensive schools now and 35 years ago. *Educational Research, Vol. 48, No. 1, March 2006*, pp. 55 – 75. Retrieved from <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/00131880500498446> dated 20-04-17
4. Maya (1976). A Study of Relationship between Attitude and Background factors of students towards their school experiences. In *Second Survey of Research in Education (1972-1978)*. New Delhi, National Council of Educational Research & Training (NCERT). 1979, p. 185.
5. Mukhopadhyaya, Swapan (1991). A study of attitude towards school in relation to interest pattern, self-concept, adjustment and scholastic achievement. In *Fifth Survey of Research in Education (1972-1978)*. New Delhi, National Council of Educational Research & Training (NCERT). 2000, p. 1889
6. Ngailiankim, Caroline (1988). An investigation into the attitude and study habits related to achievement in mathematics of class IX students in Shillong. In *Fifth Survey of Research in Education (1972-1978)*. New Delhi, National Council of Educational Research & Training (NCERT). 2000, pp. 1894-95
7. Pimplay, P.N. (1980). Profiles of Scheduled Caste Students, Punjab University Press, Chandigarh.
8. Ray, Prativa (1990). A study of student's attitude towards studies and health as related to their scholastic achievement. In *Fifth Survey of Research in Education (1972-1978)*. New Delhi, National Council of Educational Research & Training (NCERT). 2000, p. 1907

9. Rengma, Sendi Seb, Dr. Saikia, Jinamoni & Sunny, Olivia (2015). Attitude of school students towards Home work. *International Journal of Current Research*, Vol. 7, Issue, 10, pp. 21610-21612, October, 2015. Retrieved from http://journalcra.com/sites/default/files/11221_0.pdf dated 20-04-2017.
10. Sarwar, M., Bashir, M., & Alam, M. (2010). Study attitude and academic achievement at secondary level in Pakistan. *Journal of College Teaching and Learning*, Vol. 7, No. 2 – Feb 2010. pp. 55-60. Retrieved from <http://www.cluteinstitute.com/ojs/index.php/TLC/article/view/89> dated 21-04-2017
11. *Tribal Profile at a Glance* (2013). Retrieved from <http://tribal.nic.in/WriteReadData/archiveDoc/201410170113319773837STProfileataGlance.pdf> dated 25-07-2015, p.5.
12. Upadhyay, Sunil Kumar and Saxena, Alka (2008). *Upadhyay-Saxena Socio-Economic Status Scale*. Agra: H.P. Bhargava Book House.

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సోమనాధుడు

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శ్రీకృష్ణదేవరాయలు

నంది తిమ్మన

మొల్ల

కందుకూరి వీరేశలింగం

గురజాడ అప్పారావు

గిడుగు రామమూర్తి

అన్నమయ్య

బండారు అచ్చమాంబ

గుర్రం జాషువా

బోయి భీమన్న

యోగి వేమన

బద్రిరాజు కృష్ణమూర్తి

కాళోజి నారాయణరావు

జిరుదురాజు రామరాజు

సి. నారాయణరెడ్డి

దేవులపల్లి కృష్ణశాస్త్రి

శ్రీరంగం శ్రీనివాసరావు (శ్రీశ్రీ)

రావూరి భరద్వాజ్

నేదమూరి గంగాధరం

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